

OBJECT AND SUBJECT OF THE CRIME OF ATTACK

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Abstract: The article analyzes the concept, object, and subject of the crime of invasion defined in Article 164 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, different aspects of aggression from similar crimes were studied and scientifically analyzed.

Keywords: crime, trespassing, trespassing, robbery, fraud.

According to the special part of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the crime of "robbery of other people's property" differs from other types of robbery in terms of its object and objective aspect. These types of looting of other people's property are illegal possession of firearms, ammunition, explosives or detonating devices of the Special Part of the Criminal Code "Crimes against public safety" (Article 247); Illegal possession of powerful or poisonous substances (Article 251); The subject of the crime differs from the crime of illegal possession of radioactive materials (Article 252) and the crime of illegal possession of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances (Article 271) of the Criminal Code of Ukraine. Due to the fact that the illegal possession of the objects provided for in the disposition of the above-mentioned articles poses a threat to "Public safety", the current criminal law, unlike the previous criminal law, defines liability in separate chapters and separate articles. This is done correctly in terms of qualifying actions.

Thus, each illegal act can encroach and harm not only individual social relations, but also certain groups of one type of social relations included in individual relations, as well as a number of social relations protected by criminal law.

Only one social relationship does not constitute a crime that harms or endangers the interests of one victim. In this case, one of several social relations is identified as the direct object of the crime [1]. According to M.Kh. Rustamboev and B.J. Akhrorov, in these cases, they emphasize taking into account the main, additional and optional objects of criminal law protection. They say that if the legislator specifies at least one of the optional signs in the crime in the relevant article of the law, then this sign becomes a necessary sign of the crime. They say that the absence of this sign in the commission of a certain act means the absence of criminal elements in the person's act [2].

Different opinions are expressed in the legal literature about the object of the crime of invasion that we are analyzing. According to the opinions of many authors, invasion has two objects: the property of another, the life or health of citizens. But some authors, while not denying that this crime has two objects, do not recognize that the main object of invasion is the property of another. Also, according to P.B. Bakunov's emphasis, the general object of the invasion is social relations in the economic sphere. A related object is the property of another. Direct objects are: 1) appropriated property; 2) health of the victim; 3) if the invasion was committed by entering the house illegally, it is a constitutional right of the citizen, like the inviolability of residence [3].

Yu.M. Karaketov believes that the main object of the crime of aggression is a person's life and health, and personal property is an additional object, and public safety is an optional object [4].

N.A. According to Loposhenko, the most important among these objects is the human personality [5]. We cannot agree with these views. Because, in this, the authors did not take into account the characteristics of the subjective side, which is an element of the composition of the crime of invasion - ie, the motive and purpose of the crime. However, in most property crimes, including burglary, motive and purpose are necessary elements of the subjective element.

Because when the aggressor attacks the life or health of the victim, his goal is to take possession of another's property. But the owner of the property or the person responsible for the property or the persons who prevented or may prevent the taking of the property will be the main obstacle in the realization of the culprit's goal. The aggressor knows that he cannot achieve his goal without overcoming this obstacle, that is, without overcoming the resistance of the owner or the guardian of the property or the person who prevents or may prevent the taking of the property, and therefore, in order to take the property, he first attacks the health of this person in order to overcome their resistance. does.

R.Q. According to Qabulov, the main object of the crime of invasion is another's property [6]. P.B. Bakunov is of the same opinion and says that the purpose of taking possession of property is the basis for determining the main object of the invasion. M.H. Rustamboev writes that the object of invasion is other people's property, life and health of citizens [7]. These points are worthy of attention, and the necessary signs of invasion are implied.

Deprivation of a person's life is not included in the composition of the crime of invasion, if a person is killed as a result of an invasion, the act must be qualified as a total of crimes, that is, it must be qualified as a crime of invasion and intentional murder. Therefore, it is inappropriate to include a person's life as an object of crime in the crime of aggression.

Trespassing does indeed pose a threat to life, but actual damage to the object creates a different offense. From this point of view, invasion is part of crimes that endanger the health and life of a person according to its structure. The purpose of an aggressor's use of force that is dangerous to a person's health or the threat of using such force in order to take possession of another's property is unlawful possession of another's property.

A necessary element of the crime of aggression is the use of force or the threat of such force, which is dangerous to the life or health of a person. Considering this situation, it cannot be said that this risk does not harm a person.

The object of robbery of another's property is the things created as a result of human labor, economically useful, having the value of sale, purchase and exchange, created for the material and spiritual needs of a person, industrial and agricultural products, as well as Uzbek money and currency values.

Things that do not have material and exchange value lose their economic value, and taking possession of such things is not considered a crime of robbery, since these things do not have material things created by human labor, and cannot be the subject of robbery.

For example: wild animals, catching fish in rivers and lakes, cutting trees in the forest, mining underground resources. Illegal possession of these is considered a crime only in cases specified by law

If there is an animal in a special reserve, a fish bred in a special lake, these things are the subject of robbery, as well as the subject of the crime of trespass. Also, if a person who hunts wild animals, fishes in rivers and lakes or cuts down trees in the forest, while selling them or otherwise illegally acquired by another person, these things are also the subject of the crime of robbery of the property of others, including the crime of trespassing. Because, in both cases, people's work has been spent and it is the result of people's work.

The subject of robbery can be movable and immovable property. Real estate is subject only to the crimes of extortion (Article 165) and fraud (Article 168). The objects of other robbery crimes (invasion (Article 164); robbery (Article 166); robbery by embezzlement or distribution (Article 167) and theft (Article 169)) are movable property, but not immovable. Some parts of the property (door, window, etc.) can also be the subject of this act. At the time of the looting, the property in the fund of citizens, state, cooperative farms or public associations is also subject to looting.

Property that has left the owner's possession or should have come into the owner's possession or savings, but has not, cannot be the subject of robbery.

However, their illegal possession is considered a crime in the cases specified by the law and is qualified by the relevant articles of the Criminal Code.

If such items are illegally obtained from mining establishments or prospectors after mining, these items are subject to robbery, as well as the crime of trespass. Unlawful possession of documents, stamps, seals, forms that do not have an independent value in the fixed account of an enterprise, organization or institution is not considered robbery, because these things are not the subject of robbery.

If they were illegally acquired for the purpose of use, they should be qualified by the relevant articles (Articles 227 and 228) of the Civil Code. But there is also an opinion in the literature that when looting these tools, one should also pay attention to its purpose. If it is done with the aim of achieving property benefit, it should be qualified as preparation for robbery or assassination.

If the documents, stamps and seals were illegally acquired for the purpose of looting someone else's property, the action of the accused should be classified as a total of crimes, that is, Article 227 of the Criminal Code and preparation for looting someone else's property (depending on the appropriate method).

Certain documents that give the right to receive someone else's property, such as a trust deed, a receipt, a cash register, a deposit book, etc., cannot be the subject of direct robbery. If they are taken for the purpose of robbing this property, they can be considered as tools of robbery and be the subject of robbery.

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